

Descriptive Catalogue in India: a Pathway Leading to the Preservation and Dissemination of the Cultural Knowledge for the Future Generation

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Abstract

Background of the study: A descriptive catalogue of non-English books is an essential service in a country like India, where people speak more than a hundred languages across the country. It is crucial in the sense that most of the people in India are having depth knowledge in their own and regional languages.

Purpose: The main purpose of this study is to examine the library catalogues of Non-English books in the higher educational institutions in India. Cataloguing of Hindi language books is studied here since Hindi is the most popularly used language across the country.

Method: For this study, out of 44 Central Universities five Central Universities established in the North, South, East, West and Central parts of India are selected, and all these selected Universities are using Koha software for library automation purposes and are participating in INFLIBNET's IndCat Programme.

Findings: The study revealed that all these selected Universities tried for descriptive catalogue, but the proper utilisation of AACR 2 rules and MARC tags is not identified.

Conclusion: The study suggests that descriptive catalogue for non-English books by applying cataloguing codes is very essential in country like India to provide maximum access points to serve the users. Since India is a multilingual Nation with more than 100 languages spoken across the country, a descriptive catalogue for non- English books is a great challenge to the cataloguer and the Nation too, but it is an essential task which has to be implemented in the Nation to conserve the customs, cultures, languages of the Nation and also for overcome the problem of staff shortage by enabling the international exchange of bibliographic databases.

Keywords: Descriptive Catalogue, AACR, MARC, IndCat, CIP.

1. Introduction

Library, the ocean of information, where each bit of information is organized in such a way that, it will be navigated, retrieved and disseminated easily and the Library Catalogue is the important navigation tools to retrieve even a small piece of such information [14.1.6]. It is nothing but the bibliographic database for information resources in a particular Library or group of Libraries and is made available to users through Library network or on Internet.

These catalogues are constructed based on certain established standards [14.1.9]. A particular Descriptive Library Catalogues build based on standards will include each attributes of a library items, such as the name of the authors, editors, translators, contributors, title, edition, publisher, year of publication, number of pages, illustrations, its size, name of the series, call numbers etc. Such catalogue enables the users to easily locate the resources in many ways [14.1.34]. AACR and RDA (AACR successor) are the important standards for constructing such descriptive catalogue [14.1.20]. It is the AACR 2, which helped the Librarian even to overcome the language barriers in information retrieval by incorporating Parallel titles.

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2. Literature Review

Organisation of Library resources is essential for their easy accessibility and dissemination of information. Library Catalogue has to play a vital role in this area. According to **Dobreski, Brian (2021)** Standardized descriptive catalogue serve the users providing the users with the various ways to discover the resources. This also allows greater sharing and reuse of data, which will help the Information Institutions to save their time. **Chandrappa and N. S. Harinarayana (2018)** establish that the mission of the cataloguing is to facilitate the users for easy retrieval. In their study it was stated that the accurate and comprehensive catalogue data bear direct influence the effectiveness of user search of the metadata. According to them the cataloguer should give keen importance to maintain the quality of catalogue records by adhering to cataloguing codes. It will help to bring uniformity, consistency of data in catalogue records and also to decide the possible access points. The study by **Priya K. et. al (2021)** given keen importance to cataloguing of Malayalam language books in multiple languages. It was mentioned in the study that cataloguing of non-English book in multiple languages will increase its accessibility and usage. If cataloguing is done following cataloguing codes it will also help the public libraries to organize their resources systematically in Kerala State. **Riva, Pat (2022)** says that cataloguing has undergone dramatic changes, but there is still difficulty faced in providing transparent access to users despite difference in language of descriptive cataloguing and language of subject access. Several pragmatic actions can be implemented to make language less of a barrier in searching and interpreting bibliographic data. Authority control, linked authority files and controlled vocabularies have an important part play in this area. **Laksman Sarkar and Dasgupta, Sabuj (2022)** conducted an analytical study on the practice of Cataloguing of Bengali books in University Libraries in West Bengal. This paper discusses the problem faced by the different University Libraries in West Bengal in cataloguing work of Bengali Language Books. Bengali books are catalogued by the different libraries with their local modifications which creates problem in following consistency in cataloguing. Most of them using transliteration method or Roman Scripts, which cannot help users to access their required documents. This study recommends to use the standardized cataloguing format like MARC 21, for the regional language books. The study by **Mohd Ikhwan Ismail and Nurul Azurah Md. Roni (2011)** explains the problems and challenges faced in cataloguing Arabic books in Malaysian academic libraries. The study is done with personal interview with cataloguers responsible for cataloguing Arabic books. The findings shows that major problem is in the Arabic script. The cataloguer also faced problems in determination of subject heading for Arabic books that are not accurately stated in the Library of Congress Subject Heading besides the unavailability of new Arabic terms. According to the study transliteration can be one solution but is still not the best one. **Vaughan, Crystal (2018)** analyses the language of cataloguing work in the library. this study reveals that, all Librarians should recognize and reflect their own internal biases when cataloguing and make it their job to deconstruct language in cataloguing, so that every user can access their desired documents easily. Therefore, Librarian should add standardisation in Subject Heading and catalogue code for language books. In this work, **Russell, Beth M. (2003)** examined how the development of library cataloguing rules and the history of descriptive bibliography have continuously influenced rare book cataloguing codes and practices. The evolution of contemporary Anglo-American rare book cataloguing will be the major topic of this study, which will also highlight unique access points that frequently seem to exist outside the purview of library cataloguing. Amazing possibilities are provided by modern information technology, such as the ability to simultaneously index an infinite number of areas of information and link bibliographic entries to digital images of title pages. The realities of expenses, the necessity to manage substantial amounts of content, and frequently a collaborative atmosphere both inside and outside the library that has its own rules limit these possibilities. Although rare book cataloguing techniques were naturally localized in the early twentieth century, the incorporation of rare book records into online catalogues for bigger library collections has brought about a level of exposure, accountability, and collaboration that was unprecedented.

A study by **Mairaj, Muhammad Ijaz and Mukaram, Mahsham (2024)** on developing a union catalogue of Pakistani University Libraries says that University Librarians in Lahore are ready to cooperate with the development of a union catalogue, for this they seek support from the higher authorities, professional Library Associations and the Higher Education Commission of Pakistan. Although they follow cataloguing rules and MARC standards the great challenges they face are absence of standardized software, lack of funds, absence of uniform policy, professional workload and absence of standardized vocabulary. **Eiriemiokhale, Kennedy Arebamen and Oladimeji, Sodiq Olayinka (2020)** states that students of Kwara State University are pleased and appreciated the results provided by Online Public Access Catalogue and their attitude towards OPAC is positive. In a random sampling done by **Yeboah, Eugene Baah (2019)** OPAC plays a vital role in the access to information resources. The students of University of Cape Coast are aware of the OPAC but the facility is not much used by them. Infrastructural

issues and lack of relevant skills are some of the challenges preventing the optimum use of the facility. So, the study recommends for the provision of instructional materials to enhance students' search skills. According to **Eserada, Rachael Ejoywokoghene and Okolo, Stanley Efe (2019)** Use of OPAC by the students of University Libraries in South-South Nigeria is mainly to locate documents and to know the availability of document in the Library without physically visiting the Library. The study also reveals that use of OPAC by the students is low, there are lots of challenges were identified for this. The study by **Akanbi, Mohammed Lawal, Adekanbi, et al (2021)** to investigate the use and perception of Online Public Access Catalogue by users in Academic Libraries in Kwara State, Nigeria revealed that an average percentage of users can make use of library OPAC effectively and a high percentage of respondent admitted that the Library OPAC enable them to locate materials quickly on the shelf. Some of the challenges faced by the users are poor network services, power failure, poor assistance from the Library staff etc. **Ajani, Florence O. et al (2022)** investigates that Cataloguing and classification helps to provide quality Library service. It serve as bridge between the users' information needs and the information materials in the library collection, thereby improving the services rendered to the library in the area of providing quick access and retrieval of information materials and also saves the time of the users.

All the above studies clearly state the role of standardized Descriptive Library catalogue in the information retrieval, union catalogue etc. The present study is concentrating on Descriptive Catalogue in multiple languages for non- English books, especially books in Hindi language. The descriptive catalogue giving opportunity to make search in multiple languages will accelerate the search result is the theme of the study. Hindi is the 5th largest speaking language of the world [14.3.11] and is the official language of India. Descriptive catalogue of Hindi language books in both languages will help to make dynamic search in both languages.

The basic assumption of the present study is that, in India books are published in 22 languages and each established Libraries in India has to adopt the standardized Descriptive Catalogue for all these publications, then only the stated purpose of Library Catalogue can be achieved in India especially in the case of non – English books. This will help to provide more access points to the documents eliminating the language barrier between the language of descriptive catalogue and the language of the document and also help in cooperative cataloguing and union catalogue.

3. Aim of the Study

The study is carried out with the following objectives:

1. To find out how bibliographic data entry for a non-English book is generated especially for books in Hindi Language in India.
2. To analyze the extent to which cataloguing standards are implemented while creating bibliographic databases for Library resources in India
3. To study whether national exchange of bibliographic databases are possible in India and to what extent.

4. Scope of the Study

In country like India, where there are more than 100 languages spoken by people the descriptive cataloguing of Library resources with applying Cataloguing standards will help not only the Library Patrons, Librarians [14.1.11], but also the Nation for preserving its cultures, customs, languages for the future. Creating bibliographic databases in regional languages is an essential aspect in India as it will fulfill the concept "Unity in Diversity".

In Indian Libraries English language is selected for making catalogue entry, [14.2.4] but descriptive cataloguing of resources will be a blessing to both the Librarian and Patrons as it helps to enhance the information retrieval [14.1.15], as one can make search simultaneously both in his own language and in English.

If any one of the established Library in each states of India is selected as model Library for making standardized cataloguing of resources published in that particular state which include English and non-English books will help the Nation in many ways as like: easy retrieval, International exchange by enabling easy import and export, Cooperative cataloguing, Copy cataloguing, Retrospective conversion of bibliographic records [14.1.5-17] and also help to overcome the manpower shortage problem.

5. Methodology

India is a largest democratic country with diverse geographical nature, culture, customs, languages and dialects. So, we adopted a simple random sampling method to study how geographically distributed Higher Education Institutions created bibliographic data entry for books published in Hindi language.

In India there are 44 Central Universities [14.3.14] established across the country. For this study purpose only 5 Central Universities are selected and these Universities are located in the 5 regions of the Country. North- Central University of Jammu, Jammu, South- Central University of Kerala, Kerala, East- Central University of Odisha, Odisha, West- Central University of Gujarat, Gujarat, Centre-Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow.

The selected 5 Central Universities are using Koha LMS Open Source Library automation software. This helped to ensure the uniformity in MARC data elements. The selected Universities are also participating in INFLIBNET's IndCat programme.

Data for the study is collected from IndCat, a union catalogue provided by INFLIBNET, established by UGC, the apex body of the Universities in India.

For data collection the keyword "Premchand", name of the popular author in Hindi language Dhanpat Rai Srivastava famously known as Munshi Premchand was used. He has written more than 50 + novels and short stories.

The data retrieved for the keyword "Premchan" in IndCat for the above-mentioned 5 Central Universities is analysed by observing the following:

- Whether bibliographic data entry for non -English books was in multiple languages.
- The stated Universities followed AACR2 while creating Library Catalogue for Hindi language books by the author Premchand
- The utilization of basic 6 MARC tags 100 a, 245 a, 245 b, 245 c, 650 a, v, x, z, 700 a, for bibliographic data entry.

6. Descriptive Cataloguing: Applying General Cataloguing Rules

The process of creating metadata of information resources like books, movies, sound recordings, articles, etc. is called Cataloguing. There are set of rules and guidelines for cataloguing these information resources, which enable its easy retrieval and global exchange. AACR2 is one of such published codes [14.1.23], which was first published in 1978, as traditional standards for card catalogue environment [14.3.12].

The arrival of AACR2 helped much more to standardize the cataloging and also to maintain consistency in the bibliographic databases of different Libraries, as same codes are used for describe the physical attributes of library materials identically.

AACR2 was last updated in 2005 [14.3.12]. In June 2010 The Joint Steering Committee for the Revision of AACR and The Committee of Principals (CoP) decided to design a new standard for the digital environment, which led to the release of new standard RDA (Resource Description and Access) [14.1.22].

The evolution of RDA helped the cataloguer for resource description in various format like audio, video etc. Moreover, it is web-based product [14.3.12] which helps the cataloguer to bring together the bibliographic records in such a way that data will be displayed in a more meaningful way to the end users. Application of RDA has a great influence on modernization and quality of cataloguing of resources in such a way that it has enabled the exchange of data in international level [14.1.12].

In encoding Schema like MARC 21, which is the International standard for exchange of bibliographic data, changes are made to accommodate records created using RDA [14.1.25]. Some of the fields in MARC 21 are changed and some were created to support information such as content, format and support. This enabled the importing, exporting of bibliographic, and authority records in international level and easy retrieval of information [14.1.16].

7. Anglo American Cataloguing Rules

7.1 AACR2- General Rules for Description

1.0 D2. Second Level of Description,

1.0D2. Second Level of Description. For the Second level of description, include at least the elements set out in this schematic illustration:

Title proper [general material designation] = Parallel title: other title information / first statement of responsibility; each subsequent statement of responsibility. – Edition statement / first statement of responsibility relating to the edition. – Material or type of publication/ specific details. – first place of publication, etc.: first publisher, etc., date of publication, etc. – Extent of item: other physical details; dimensions. – (Title proper of series / statement of responsibility relating to series, ISSN of series numbering within the series. Title of subseries, ISSN of subseries; numbering within subseries). –Note(s). – Standard number [14.2.2.]

8. Descriptive Catalogue of Non -English Books in Indian Scenario: A Comparative Study

The 28 states and seven union territories of India with unique customs and traditions, is mainly set up on linguistic principles [14.3.7]. As of today, the Indian constitution recognizes 22 major languages of India in what is known as “the 8th Schedule” of the Constitution. They also happen to be the major literary languages in India, with a considerable volume of writing in them [14.3.7]. Books are being published all over India in all these languages. The book published in each language reflects the culture, customs of various parts of the Nation.

In India English is chosen as the favoured language for making entries in Catalogue, the descriptive cataloguing of these books published in various languages in India, at least the major 22 languages will be very much helpful for the Librarian and the users to overcome the language barriers [14.1.28], at the same time to preserve the culture, customs and languages.

The present study was conducted by selecting Libraries of higher educational institutions like Central Universities, since, there are necessary Library staffs, qualified cataloguers, standardized catalogues, Web OPACs and most of the databases are available in IndCat.

Further the study was limited to following five Central Universities situated in the 5 regions like North, East, West, South and Central part of India. All these selected Universities are participating in IndCat and are using Koha Integrated Library Management System for the automation purpose.

- ❖ Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow
- ❖ Central University of Gujarat, Gujarat
- ❖ Central University of Jammu, Jammu
- ❖ Central University of Kerala, Kerala
- ❖ Central University of Odisha, Odisha

In this study bibliographic data entry for Hindi language book, the Official language of Central Government, India, available in IndCat for the most famous Hindi author Munshi Premchand is analysed.

8.1 Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow:

For the keyword “Premchand” in IndCat 8 records were retrieved. Out of 8 records in 4 records title entry was done in Hindi language. The concerned title is not either translated or transliterated to English language.

It is also found that only title entry was done in Hindi language but the author entry is not in Hindi language.

The cataloguer made an attempt to make bibliographic data entry for the title in a language as it occurs in title page, but did not attempt to make entry in English language also.

8.2 Central University of Gujarat, Gujarat:

For the keyword “Premchand” in IndCat 51 records are retrieved. All the records are in English language only.

The cataloguer did not made attempt to make bibliographic data entry in multiple languages as per the provision in cataloguing standards.

8.3 Central University of Jammu, Jammu:

For the keyword “Premchand” in IndCat 58 records are retrieved. All the records are in English language only.

The cataloguer did not made attempt to make bibliographic data entry in multiple languages as per the

provision in cataloguing standards.

8.4 Central University of Kerala, Kerala:

For the keyword “Premchand” in IndCat 25 records are retrieved. For 18 records bibliographic data entry was made in English language only. For 7 records bibliographic data entry is made in multiple languages (Title was entered in both Hindi language as it occurs in title page and in English language [transliterated]. Entries in both languages are distinguished by ‘=’ sign). For these 7 records data entry of author name was made in multiple languages and in some records subject added entry was also made in multiple languages. The Central University of Kerala used MARC Tag 100a to enter the author name as it occurs in the title page, MARC Tag 245c was used to enter author name in English language. MARC Tag 700a is used to give data entry for translator, editor in original language as it occurs in title page.

The cataloguer made an attempt to make data entry in multiple languages. The bibliographic data entry for title, author and subject added entry is in multiple languages.

The cataloguer tried to implement the provision in cataloguing standard like AACR2: *1.0D2. Second Level of Description [14.2.2]* to some extent.

But the exact implementation was not done as the cataloguer preferred transliteration instead of actual translation.

8.5 Central University of Odisha, Odisha:

For the keyword “Premchand” in IndCat 39 records are retrieved. Almost in all the records, title is entered in Hindi language as it occurs in title page with transliterated English title in brackets (). For 10 records subject added entry is in multiple languages (Hindi and English).

The cataloguer attempted to make bibliographic data entry in multiple languages (title entry in original language as it occurs in the title page, then it transliterated to English language). The cataloguer also tried to make subject added entry in multiple languages (both in Hindi and English).

The cataloguer while opting to make bibliographic data entry in multiple language did not attempted to implement the cataloguing standard rule as such.

9. Errors found in Cataloguing of Hindi Language Books

The following are some of the major errors identified in the MARC Tag 100, 245 and 650 while creating the bibliographic data entry for works of Munshi Premchand in Hindi language:

- ❖ **Personal name:** There are errors identified in the choice of rendering and recording the name of the author. Some of the University recorded the author name in MARC Tag 100 a as Premchand, some as प्रेमचंद, while others as Premchand, Munshi. The original name of the author i.e. **Dhanpat Rai Srivastava** is not mentioned by any of the University either in MARC Tag 100 a or in MARC Tag 700 a.
- ❖ **Title:** Some Libraries opted only English language (transliteration of Hindi language) for making title entry in MARC Tag 245 a, Some Libraries recorded title in Hindi language only, while others created title entry in both English language (transliteration) and in Hindi language. The title proper and parallel title are differentiated by some Universities by using brackets (), while others used = sign. At the same time it is noted that title proper and parallel title are entered in the same MARC Tag 245 a.
- ❖ **Subject added entry--topical term:** Detailed subject description is recorded by some Universities only. It is also noted that most of the Universities recorded Subject description in MARC Tag 650 in English language only. Some recorded Subject description in MARC Tag 650 in both Hindi and English language.

10. Findings

From above study it has been found that cataloguing rules as such is not implemented in any of the Universities. It has also found that, most of the Universities made bibliographic data entry for Hindi books in English language only.

It has also be noted that some of the Universities tried to make entries for non-English books in the language at least title as it occurs in title page, but all of them selected transliteration instead of actual translation. Some of the Universities used “=” sign to distinguish title Proper and Parallel title as per AACR 2 Second Level Description, [14.2.2] but it has been found that they used the “=” sign in the same MARC tag 245a instead of 245a for title proper and 245b for Parallel title as follow:

Table 1. AACR2R Second Level Description and MARC Format

Second level description AACR2R	MARC format
Title proper = Parallel title: other title information	245 XX \$a Title = \$b Parallel title : other title information

The study also finds that, if in India AACR 2 Second Level Description” title Proper [general material designation] = Parallel title” [14.2.2] as such implemented with translation to English, it will create problems, as there are more than 100 languages spoken across the country. The country has to recruit language experts in each language, which will be a burden to the Nation, at the same time the users of the database also require good language knowledge, and otherwise the efforts will be a waste to the country. But it also identified that, actual translation will help to overcome the problem of spelling mismatch as usually occurs in transliteration, it is also important while making data entry in software like Koha which is sensitive.

The study comes to the finding that although there is 000-900 tag in MARC most of the Universities are using limited Tags for bibliographic data entry. It is found that the below mentioned Tags are most popularly used Tags:

Table 2. Mark Tags and Description

Sl No.	Tag	Descriptions
1.	100 a	Personal name
2.	245 a	Title
3.	245 b	Reminder of title
4.	245 c	Statement of responsibility, etc.
5.	260 a, b, c	Publication, Distribution, etc. (imprint)
6.	300 a, b, c	Physical Description
7.	650 a, v, x, z	Subject added entry--topical term
8.	700 a	Added entry- Personal name

11. Recommendations

It is suggested that, in developing countries like India with rich culture and language diversity, Central Universities established in each State can be converted to Regional Centre for cataloguing all the non-English books published in that particular state with regional languages experts. Although India has National Library at Calcutta, and all the published works reaches to the concerned Library as per constitution of India, still there are lots of problems for a common man to reach to the publications, since they are not properly catalogued due to various issues.

Government of India can amend the Copyright Law in such a way that all the books published in the particular state should be sent to the authorized Regional Centre, for bibliographic data entry following certain cataloguing standards strictly. Thus it is made possible for a country to get a centralized multilingual bibliographic database like “PARIVAHAN SEWA” [14.3.9] for the entire Indian publications. It is also suggested that it should be made mandatory for a Publisher/Offset Press to get Cataloging in Publication for each books which is not yet been published, from the authorized regional centers. There by enabling the book processing an easy task with CIP data on the copyright page included by the publisher [14.3.13].

12. Conclusion

The various traditions, customs of various parts of India are being published in various languages from each part of the country and it has to be preserved and conserved for the future generation. The language is the main barrier for it to be happening, as most of the publication will be in the regional language. Library, as an important information hub has a main role to be played here. With a standardized Library catalogue, Library should help the common people by providing access to all the publications in the Nation in their own languages [14.1.4].

A Library Catalogue must act as a vital tool for bridging the gap between the information need by a user and the Library resources. So, the Libraries established in each state, at least, the Central Universities should start its work with creating bibliographic data entry in multiple languages for non –English books. So that, the resource will reach to the wide audience and its usage will be optimised, thereby the culture of India is preserved which is reflected in each publications. It is very crucial in India with rich culture and languages to bring unity in diversity.

The standardized Descriptive Cataloguing not only help to provide effective library services, but also help in national exchange of bibliographic databases [14.1.7], which is the necessity of most of the Indian Libraries to overcome the main problem of staff shortage by enabling importing or exporting of bibliographic and authority records, as it is from Library of Congress. Simultaneously financial problems and duplicate work can be eliminated forever in this area.

In a country like India further research is very much required in the area of descriptive catalogue of non- English books, as all over in India more than 100 languages are spoken by people and Indian constitution recognizes 22 major languages. With a standardized Descriptive Library Catalogue of non-English documents in multiple languages, the each Library is not only serve its users but also the Nation to preserve its language and culture. It will also help in providing easy access and dissemination of information by providing easy access points in multiple languages to the non- English resources which is published in various languages from various parts of the country. Otherwise the information seekers should go for English translation of the non- English documents which is not easy for every users other than he/she is experts in English language or one should go for transliteration to English language, this will create problem in spell the words correctly. This will create problem in information retrieval especially while making search in software like Koha, which is case sensitive.

The exact implication of Descriptive Library Catalogue in multiple languages for non –English books in India is not an easy task also, as there are books published in more than twenty languages. Each Library should appoint language experts who have got thorough knowledge in English and the concerned language, which will create financial burden to the Nation like India. But the Nation can overcome the problem to some extent by converting some National important Library as a regional centre for making Descriptive Catalogue of non-English books in multiple languages and making it mandatory to send a copy of all the publications to the regional centres or the Publisher/Offset Press in India are compelled to get Cataloging in Publication for each books which is not yet been published, from the authorized regional centers.

13. Limitation of the Study

In India, according to All India Survey on Higher Education, there are 1302 Universities, 50719 Colleges, 14004 Standalone institutes with 158 Institute of National Importance [14.3.8]. So, the present study is limited to Central Universities. Out of 44 Central Universities 5 Central Universities located in the North, South, East, West and Central regions of the Country which are diverse in customs, culture and language are randomly selected for the study.

The Indian constitution recognizes 22 major languages (1) Assamese, (2) Bengali, (3) Gujarati, (4) Hindi, (5) Kannada, (6) Kashmiri, (7) Konkani, (8) Malayalam, (9) Manipuri, (10) Marathi, (11) Nepali, (12) Oriya, (13) Punjabi, (14) Sanskrit, (15) Sindhi, (16) Tamil, (17) Telugu, (18) Urdu (19) Bodo, (20) Santhali, (21) Maithili and (22) Dogri. Books are published in all these languages. Hindi language is selected for the study since, Hindi is the Official language of Central Government, India and is the 5th largest speaking language of the world.

Acknowledgments

We would like to acknowledge and thank all those who have given valuable contributions to this study.

Authors' Contributions

All authors have contributed to the final manuscript. The contribution of all authors: conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, writing original draft preparation, writing review and editing. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

All authors have no conflict of interest related to this study.

Funding

This study did not receive any funding.

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14.1 Journal Article

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